

Formulation and Evaluation of Mucoadhesive Buccal Patches of Venlafaxine

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ABSTRACT

Buccal drug delivery has been proposed as an alternative to per-oral and parenteral administration of drugs. Patches are laminates that contain an impermeable backing layer. Drug-containing reservoir layer and a bioadhesive surface for mucosal attachment. Today, research is more focused on the development of suitable delivery systems for drugs that undergo first-pass metabolism, such as beta-blocking agents, cardiovascular drugs, analgesics, and peptides. Additionally, studies have been conducted on the development of controlled or slow-release delivery systems for local therapy of diseases in the oral cavity. In which delivery of a drug occurs through the mucosal membrane lining the cheeks. Buccal mucosa is a novel route of drug administration. Venlafaxine is used for depression. Oral administration of venlafaxine has many disadvantages. So, designed bilayered mucoadhesive buccal patch was designed using a hydrophilic polymer. To carry out stability studies, reduce the frequency of administration, increase the residence time of the dosage form, and give sustained release of the drug, which satisfies the antidepressant effect.[1].

Keywords: mucoadhesive, antidepressants, buccal patches, hydrophilic polymer, sustained release.

INTRODUCTION

Oral drug delivery is the most widely utilized route of administration among all the routes that have been explored for systemic delivery of drugs via pharmaceutical products of different dosage forms. The oral route is considered most natural, convenient, and safe due to its ease of administration, patient acceptance, and cost-effective manufacturing process. Pharmaceutical products designed for oral delivery are mainly immediate-release type or conventional drug delivery systems, which are designed for immediate release of the drug for rapid absorption. These immediate-release dosage forms have some limitations, such as:

- 1) Drugs with short half-lives require frequent administration, which increases the chances of missing a dose of the drug, leading to poor patient compliance.
- 2) A typical peak-valley plasma conc. A time profile is obtained, which makes the attainment of a steady state condition difficult.

- 3) The unavoidable fluctuations in the drug concentration may lead to under-medication or over-medication as the C_{ss} values fall or rise beyond the therapeutic range.[2]

The fluctuating drug levels may lead to precipitation of adverse effects, especially of a drug with a small therapeutic index, whenever over-medication occurs. Controlled drug delivery systems can include the maintenance of drug levels within a desired range, the need for fewer administrations, optimal use of the drug in question, and increased patient compliance. While these advantages can be significant, the potential disadvantages cannot be ignored, like the possible toxicity or non-biocompatibility of the materials used, undesirable by-products of degradation, any surgery required to implant or remove the system, the chance of patient discomfort from the delivery device, and the higher cost of controlled-release systems compared with traditional pharmaceutical formulations. The ideal drug delivery system should be inert, biocompatible, mechanically strong, comfortable for the patient, capable of achieving high drug loading, safe from accidental release, simple to administer and remove, and easy to

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fabricate and sterilize. The goal of many of the original controlled-release systems was to achieve a delivery profile that would yield a high blood level of the drug over a long period of time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Preparation of mucoadhesive bilayered buccal patches

a) Backing Layer: For preparing a formulation, a glass Petri plate of 7 cm diameter was used as a casting surface. Initially, a backing membrane of ethyl cellulose was fabricated by slowly pouring a solution containing 400 mg of ethyl cellulose and 2% dibutyl phthalate in 10 ml of acetone into a glass Petri plate and air drying for 1 h.

b) Mucoadhesive layer containing drug: Buccal patches of venlafaxine were prepared by the solvent casting technique

Fig. venlafaxine buccal patch

Various steps involved in the preparation of mucoadhesive buccal patches are as follows:[3]

1. Calculation of drug quantity for 30 ml solution:

A 7 cm diameter glass Petri plate was used as a casting surface. So the total area of the surface was calculated and found to be,

Formula:

$$\text{Total surface area of casting surface} = A = \pi r^2$$

R = radius of glass Petri plate (3.5 cm)

$$A = \pi (3.5)^2 = 38.465 \text{ cm}^2$$

The desired quantity of venlafaxine was 10 mg (dose of drug) per 4 cm² buccal patch. Therefore quantity required for a 30 ml solution to be poured on a 38.465 cm² area was calculated and found to be,

$$\text{Calculation: } 10 \text{ mg} \quad - \quad 4 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$? \text{ mg} \quad - \quad 38.465 \text{ cm}^2$$

$$? = 38.465 \times 10 / 4 = 96.16 \text{ mg}$$

(b) Preparation of drug and polymer solution:

Weighed amount of tamarind gum was added to 10 ml of water and heated till the gum dissolved. The hydrophilic polymer PVA was then added to this solution and kept aside for 20 min for swelling of the polymer. Further HPMC E-15 was added to it and the solution was kept in the refrigerator for the purpose of cooling (since HPMC dissolves in cold water) for 2-3 h till a clear solution was obtained. 0.3% chitosan was dissolved in 10 ml of 1.5% w/v glacial acetic acid. The above two solutions were mixed together in one beaker. Later, PG (40% w/w of polymers) was added as a plasticizer to the solution with constant stirring using a constant mechanical stirrer for 10-15 min. Accurately weighed quantity (96.16 mg) of venlafaxine was dissolved in 10 ml of distilled water, and it was added to the above solution.[4]

2. Deaeration of the solution:

The solution of the drug and polymer was then kept overnight to get a clear, bubble-free solution.

3. Transfer of the appropriate volume of solution into a mold and drying of the solution:

The resultant solution was then cast on the backing layer of ethyl cellulose in a glass Petri plate and allowed to dry in a hot air oven, maintained at 50 till a dried patch was formed.

4. Cutting the final dosage form to contain the desired amount of drug:

The dried patches were then cut into rectangular pieces of size of 2 cm, with a total surface area of 4 cm².

5. Packaging of the patches:

The samples were packed in aluminium foil and stored in amber colored glass container. They were maintained at room temperature and 60% RH; this condition maintained the integrity and elasticity of buccal patches.[5]

EVALUATION OF BUCCAL PATCH

1. Physical appearance:

Patches of each formulation were randomly selected and visually inspected for texture by feel or touch.

2. Thickness and weight uniformity:

The thickness of patches was assessed using a vernier caliper with a least count of 0.01 mm. For each formulation, three randomly selected patches with a surface area of 4 cm² were used. Each patch was weighed individually on an analytical balance, and the average weights were calculated.

3. Surface pH measurement:

The surface pH of the buccal compacts was determined in order to investigate the possibility of any.

4. Drug Content Uniformity:

The patches were tested for drug content uniformity by the UV Spectrophotometric method. Patches were cut from three different places from the cast patches. Each patch was placed in a 100 ml volumetric flask and dissolved in pH 6.8 PBS and filtered through Whatman filter paper. From the solution, 1 ml was taken and diluted with pH 6.8 PBS up to 10 ml, to make a final concentration of 10 µg/ml. The absorbance of the solution was measured at 226.1 nm using a UV/visible spectrophotometer. The percentage drug content was determined using the standard graph, and the same procedure was repeated for three patches of each formulation.[6]

5. Tensile strength:

Tensile strength of the patches was checked by a texture analyser equipped with a 10 kg load cell. The film of 200 mm² was randomly selected and was fixed

between the two clamps of the probe for a hold time of 60 s. The lower clamp was held stationary, and the patch was pulled apart by the upper clamp. It was pulled at a speed with side effects *in vivo*. As an acidic or alkaline pH may irritate the buccal mucosa, the surface pH should be as close to neutral as possible. Surface pH of the patch was determined to check whether the patch causes irritation to the mucosa. The surface pH study was carried out by selecting 3 patches randomly. pH measurement was done using a pH meter. In this method pH probe was placed in close contact with the wetted patch surface, and pH was recorded for each film.

6. Folding endurance:

Folding endurance of patches was determined manually by repeatedly folding a film at the same place until it ruptured or was folded 350 times, whichever is less. The number of folds required to break or crack a patch was taken as the folding endurance. The experiments were performed in triplicate, and average values were reported^[7]

7. % Swelling index:

The degree of swelling of the bioadhesive polymer is an important factor affecting adhesion. The swelling index of the buccoadhesive patch was evaluated by placing the films in PBS pH 6.8 at 37 ± 1 °C. Three patches of each batch were cut and weighed, and the average initial weight was calculated as W₁. The patches were placed in PBS and were removed at time intervals of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, and 60 minutes till there was a maximum increase in weight of the patches; excess water on the surface was carefully absorbed using filter paper, and swollen patches were reweighed.²¹ The average weight W₂ was calculated, and the swelling index was calculated by the formula:

$$\text{Swelling index} = 100 \times (W_2 - W_1 / W_1)$$

8. Accelerated Stability Studies:

The stability studies were conducted according to ICH guidelines to investigate the effect of temperature, relative humidity on the drug in different formulations. The final optimized formulation was subjected to aggravated conditions of temperature and

relative humidity by wrapping it in aluminium foil and packaging it in a glass container. The buccal patches were kept in a stability chamber, at $40 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ temperature and $75 \pm 5\%$ RH for 3 months respectively. After 1, 2, and 3 months, buccal patches were tested for:

1. Changes in the appearance
2. Mucoadhesive strength
3. Drug content
4. Release behavior

Change in the surface pH [8]

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preformulation Studies:

Characterization of venlafaxine:

A. Color: Venlafaxine was observed and found to be white in color.

B. Taste and Odor: Taste was bitter and odorless.

C. Melting Point: The melting point of venlafaxine was found to be 214.0.

D. U. V. Spectrum: Drug showed its maximum absorbance at 226.1 nm, in PBS solution pH 6.8 (Fig.1) and 225.5 nm in 0.1 N HCl (Fig. 2)

Fig. UV spectrum of venlafaxine in phosphate buffer of pH 6.8

Fig.2: UV spectrum of venlafaxine in 0.1 N HCl

Differential scanning calorimetry:

DSC thermograms of pure drug venlafaxine and drug excipients are shown in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. Results have shown that a sharp exothermic peak was observed of the drug individually at 213.66°C , corresponding to its melting point (214°C -2170). For the sample containing the drug and selected excipients mixture, a sharp peak was observed of the drug at 210.23°C with a reduction in peak intensity. Thus, as there was not a significant shift in the exothermic peak of the drug as that obtained from the individual drug sample, it can be concluded that there was no interaction occurred between the excipients and drug venlafaxine. Thus, the drug venlafaxine was found to be compatible with the selected excipients.[9]

Fig. 3: Thermogram of pure drug venlafaxine

Fig. 4: Thermogram of venlafaxine drug and excipients mixture

iii. Assay of Drug Content:

The assay of the drug present along with the excipients. Assay was performed using a UV Spectrophotometer. There was no significant change in drug assay done initially and after 30 days (Table 7.4), it can be concluded that there was no interaction between the drug and selected excipients.

Evaluation parameters	Results
Appearance	Smooth
Weight	0.54 ± 0.01 mg
Thickness	119.53 ± 1.00 mm
pH	6.80 ± 0.07
Tensile strength	10.79 N
Folding endurance	320.6 ± 1.52
Drug content uniformity	9.89 ± 0.04
Swelling index	195.55%

Accelerated Stability Studies:

The results of stability studies performed on batch A3 are shown in the above Table. After the 3-month study, it was found that there was no change in the appearance of the patch and a negligible change in pH and mucoadhesive strength. The drug content and % drug release after 3 months were decreased but not significantly.[10]

CONCLUSION

The present study successfully formulated and evaluated mucoadhesive buccal patches containing venlafaxine for controlled drug delivery. The patches were prepared using suitable polymers that provided desired flexibility, uniformity, and satisfactory mucoadhesive strength. Evaluation parameters such as thickness, folding endurance, surface pH, and drug content uniformity indicated that the formulation met the required pharmaceutical standard. Among the prepared formulations, the optimized patch exhibited sustained drug release with good mucoadhesive properties and patient-friendly characteristics. Therefore, the study concluded that mucoadhesive buccal patches of venlafaxine can serve as a promising alternative drug delivery system to enhance bioavailability, avoid first-pass metabolism, and provide prolonged therapeutic action.[11]

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